

A NOVEL TECHNIQUE FOR THE CONSERVATION OF LARGE TILED PANELS

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Introduction

This article discusses a new process for carefully removing large, heavy, decorative tiled panels from masonry walls, a process which was adapted from one previously developed for the removal of 'signature panels' from plastered walls due for demolition. The technique was applied on an 'industrial' scale, over a relatively short time frame, to 68 panels. It involved use of specialist cutting and lifting machinery, co-ordination of a number of large team of conservators, and strict adherence to architects' and building contractors' timetables.

Late in 2001, Eura Conservation was asked to look at the possibility of saving some signature panels from the shortly-to-be-demolished Manchester Free Trade Hall (FTH). The signatures were in pencil on rendered plaster and were signed by some of the musicians who had appeared in the hall since its post-war rebuild in the early 1950s. A successful technique was developed and the panels are now on display in the Radisson Edwardian Hotel, built on the site of the old FTH. In 2009 Eura was asked if the technique could be modified for use in another project, involving the safe removal of ceramic tile panels from a hospital. The answer was 'probably yes', although some development work would be required.

The need for intervention

Two children's wards, containing 68 Doulton tiled panels, were due to be demolished as part of a re-development of the Royal Victoria Infirmary in Newcastle. One of the great benefits of ceramics is that the colours often remain as fresh and vibrant as the day they were first created and this is certainly the case with this fabulous collection.

Most of the panels depict traditional nursery rhymes and were painted by artists such as William Rowe, JH McLennan and Margaret E Thompson. Similar panels can be found on the walls of the Sassoon Hospital in Poona, India, as well as the Wellington Hospital, in New Zealand, which has recently conserved 18 panels. The Newcastle collection is significant, however, in that it comprises no less than 57 story panels, together with 9 panels depicting rural scenes and 2 text panels showing the names of the wards. There are a further 18 text panels in other parts of the hospital. It is thought to be the largest such collection in the world. The collection is of further importance in that it is a snapshot of the Edwardian age: illustrative of the role played by rhymes and stories in childrens' education, of attitudes towards the infirm and of social philanthropy.

Figure 1 One of the Doulton nursery rhyme panels before removal

The choice of conservation process

The traditional approach to the task of removing tiled panels is to cut along the line of grout, freeing each tile from the matrix of its fellow tiles. This ensures that any cracking will be contained and limited to an individual tile. The conservator then prises the tile from its matrix. There are a number of difficulties and risks associated with this process. The technique relies on a minimum gap width between each tile that is larger than the cutting width of the blade, so that the grout might be cut without damaging the tile glaze on each side of the kerf. The chief risk, however, is that the conservator has to attempt by trial and error to prise or lever a very hard, brittle object off a similarly hard underlying surface. Commonly the process brings about cracked tiles. Furthermore, because it separates the panel into multiple pieces, there is also the risk that parts may over time become lost or the orientation of components confused.

A different process was developed for the removal of the signature panels from FTH which addressed the fact that as there were no joint lines to cut along, the panels had to be removed in one piece. If a similar technique could be developed for the tiled panels, it should result in reduced irrevocable treatment and increased efficiency. The objective of the new technique would therefore be the removal of an entire panel in one go, with a sufficient layer of cementitious backing retained in place to prevent flexing and separation of individual tiles along the lines of the grout. This was to be achieved using a combination of frontal facing & support and diamond-wire cutting through the entire backing of the mortar matrix.

The new process

To achieve the cutting action a continuous loop of diamond-coated wire is mounted on a number of pulleys, one or more being motorised. Between two of the pulleys there is a large span of wire that performs the cutting as it comes into contact with the target material until the cut is complete. Diamond wire is chosen as it is able to saw through virtually any material. As the wire cuts, it is pulled through the structure like a cheese wire. Obviously considerable care has to be taken to ensure that the wire does not come into contact with any of the tiles to be conserved.

In Manchester, the signature panels were supported during removal by carefully pre-fitted mild steel frames. While this technique worked perfectly, the tiled panels in Newcastle are significantly larger. Consequently, a series of workshop trials were conducted on specially prepared 'mock' tile panels. These tests were chiefly concerned with developing a means of adhering a rigid surface to the face of the tiles, in such a way that the weight of the entire panel could be borne in tension by the adhesive/consolidant. The adhesive had to be fully reversible, and to cause no adverse reaction to the tiles. The final choice was a 20% solution of acetone and Paraloid B72. It gave a pull-off test value in excess 10 kN/m² and was wholly reversible.

Figure 2 Conducting a lifting and adherence test

On the hospital site, each panel was surveyed and any site-specific requirements noted. The perimeter of each panel had been bordered in recent times with a 50 mm wide pine frame, mitred at the corners, and screwed through into the wall. These

were removed to reveal very many old holes in the tiles and a general thin covering of plaster and paint. This was removed with a proprietary dichloromethane paint stripper.

After the surface had been checked for painted plaster repairs (often found on old panels) the tiles were cleaned with acetone. A border was then marked around the outermost part of the panel with a chinagraph waxed pencil. This border provided a safe perimeter for the picture tiles. Any areas of grout that appeared to be missing were then re-instated, to ensure a uniform matrix of tiles.

A barrier coat of 20% Paraloid B72 and acetone was then applied with a wide brush to the entire surface of the panel. This was to serve as a removable barrier coat between the tiles and a layer of glass-fibre woven matting bonded with 20% Paraloid B72 and acetone. Small urethane foam pads were placed into position at regular intervals on the surface of the rigid matting once the B72 and fibreglass matting had completely solidified.

A 25mm marine plywood sheet, which had been pre-cut to the exact dimensions of the tile panel, was then placed into position covering the tiled panel, with the bottom edge of the plywood resting on two lengths of all-thread, which had been resin-fixed into the wall. The plywood panel itself had also been pre-drilled with a regularly spaced series of 12mm diameter holes. A series of horizontal timber battens was then fastened to the wall, in the same manner as the all-thread. These battens held the plywood sheeting firmly against the foam spacers. The plywood panel was then bonded to the consolidated and protected surface using aerosol polyurethane foam, injected through the holes in the plywood. The timber battens held the plywood panel firmly in place while the foam expanded and cured. Once the foam had cured, the battens were removed and a bespoke aluminium lifting-frame was screwed to the plywood panel.

The next stage was to accurately chase four 30 mm wide slots around the entire panel, to a depth of 45-50mm. These slots determined the final size of the tile panel. Meanwhile, sufficient space had to be created in the ceiling above the panel to enable aluminium 'I' beam to be placed into a pocket in the wall. The plywood panel over the tiles acted as protection for the panel in this procedure.

To allow the diamond wire cutter to operate, a number of square chases, roughly 150mm x 150mm, had to be cut in the wall to accommodate the pulley mechanisms. The machine was now carefully positioned and anchored in place, with the diamond wire resting in the upper horizontal chase above the panel.

Figure 3 A panel covered with fibreglass Paraloid, fibre-glass matting and cushion pads

Figure 4 The diamond wire cutter installed. The panel has now been protected with a plywood sheet

Figure 5 Close-up of the cutting operation

Figure 6 A panel has been cut through and is being lowered

The initial cuts to seat the wire and ensure it wouldn't jump out of the slot were accomplished by hand. The machine then cut downwards through the mortar, at a distance of 30mm from the front face of the tiled panel. Once the machine had cut through around 75 percent of the panel, cutting was temporarily halted. A scaffold tower was erected in place and the aluminium beam was placed in position above the panel, supported by the tower and the previously excavated wall pocket. The panel

was fastened by a sling attached to a 500kg swl chain hoist on the beam and to the lifting frame on the panel. The sling was then pre-tensioned to accept the anticipated weight of the panel. Cutting then recommenced and continued until the panel was free from the wall.

The panel could then be lowered into a packing case and placed in safe store.

The panels after removal

The panels were removed from the hospital and transported to conservation workshops. Each panel was unpacked and placed facedown on the bed of a masonry plane. The cementitious matrix on the back of the tiles, which up until now bore the marks of the cutting wire, was now abrasively planed into a completely flat and level surface. This surface allowed the panel to be refastened to another 25mm sheet of plywood which would act as the final display substrate without creating any undue pressure points on the original tiles. The panel was then turned over so the “lifting system” could be removed. This involved unscrewing the lifting frame, sawing through the polyurethane foam with a soft saw, peeling off the Paraloid reinforced glass fibre and removing the remains of the Paraloid. The panel was then mounted in a stainless steel frame containing an internal green frame, designed to reflect the original framing tiles.

Other than possibly making aesthetic repairs to 1970’s screw holes, no other conservation treatment was necessary.

Future applications of the process

This technique was developed to suit a particular set of circumstances. It combined efficiency of labour, relatively low cost, and speed, whilst minimising irrevocable treatment of the objects. All consumable materials were easily sourced, inexpensive, and presented no threats to the object. Neither were there any difficult ethical conservation decisions to be made over the need to cut brickwork and drill chases in the surrounding wall because the building was destined for demolition. The diamond cutting process was lubricated with water and the cutting of chases generated some dust. Both of these potential pollutants were satisfactorily controlled in this situation, but might be less easy in other situations. Further, the success of the technique also relies on the strength of the bond between the glazes and the body of the tile. Therefore the significance of the surrounding building and the exact nature of the tiles would have to be considered before this technique could be safely used on other similar projects, although these issues should be relatively easily resolved.

Figure 7 A panel following completion of the process